

Application of Artificial Intelligence and Computer Vision for Non-Invasive Fish Health Monitoring

Sumaiya Khatib¹, Qureshi Seema², Rais Sharifunnisa³ & Khan Tasmiya⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Department of Zoology, G. M. Momin Women's College, Bhiwandi

Corresponding Author – Sumaiya Khatib

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18217888

Abstract:

Aquaculture is one of the fastest-growing food production sectors worldwide and plays a vital role in food security and livelihoods. However, intensive farming practices with high stocking densities often result in immediate disease transmission and fish mortality. Traditional fish health monitoring methods rely on capturing and handling fish, which can cause stress and increase the risk of infection. This review highlights the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and computer vision as effective tools for modern aquaculture management. By using underwater cameras and environmental sensors, AI systems enable continuous and non-invasive monitoring of fish health. These technologies can detect physical injuries, abnormal swimming behaviour, and changes in water quality in real time, enabling early disease detection and timely management. AI is not intended to replace the knowledge of fish farmers but to support decision-making as an intelligent monitoring assistant. AI-based monitoring systems have the potential to improve fish welfare, reduce economic losses, and promote sustainable aquaculture production.

Keywords: Aquaculture, Artificial Intelligence, Computer Vision, Fish Health Monitoring, Disease Detection, Water Quality.

Introduction:

Fishes play a critical role in global food security and livelihoods, supporting people worldwide (FAO, 2022; HLPE, 2014), thus making it crucial to preserve this global food source (Béné *et al.*, 2015). This industry has experienced rapid growth in recent decades, driven by the increasing global demand for seafood (Tacon & Metian, 2015). This rapid intensification is commonly associated with high stocking densities and limited visibility, making continuous monitoring of individual fish in ponds and tanks increasingly challenging (FAO, 2020; Badiola *et al.*, 2012). However, the rapid expansion of aquaculture has also brought challenges, including rising production costs, environmental degradation, and resource inefficiencies, which threaten its long-term sustainability (Naylor *et al.*, 2021). Pollution, climate change, farming practices, regulatory issues, water quality and diseases affect aquaculture

production (Bondad-Reantaso *et al.*, 2020). Live feeds, probiotics, prebiotics, algae, rotifers and other supplements are also used to maintain health and increase production (Ringø *et al.*, 2020). In many aquaculture operations, disease outbreaks are often detected only after visible clinical signs appear, by that time fish mortality, reduced feeding, and substantial economic losses have already occurred (Shinn *et al.*, 2015). Fish diseases cause billions in global losses, making early detection and regular health checks essential (Shinn *et al.*, 2015; Bohara *et al.*, 2024). Traditionally, farmers monitor health by visual observation from the surface or by sampling a few fish to inspect them manually. This method has two significant flaws: firstly, it is reactive, as farmers usually only notice problems when fish stop feeding or start dying (Saberioon *et al.*, 2017); and secondly it is stressful, as netting and handling fish removes their protective slime coat (mucus), making them more susceptible to

secondary infections and reducing their immune response (Barton *et al.*, 2002). In this context, artificial intelligence (AI) can be understood as a data-driven decision support tool that continuously analyses visual and sensor-based information, functioning as a 24-hour monitoring assistant rather than a physical robotic system (Li *et al.*, 2023a). With improvements in computerized models, remote sensing, AI, machine learning and the Internet of Things (Damodar *et al.*, 2023; Stofa *et al.*, 2025), freshwater and marine aquaculture is revolutionizing worldwide. Classifying and detecting aquatic animals using manual methods is time-consuming, whereas deep learning-based technology automates these complex tasks without human intervention (Maluazi, Zulkifley & Kadim, 2024). This paper examines the application of artificial intelligence-based systems, particularly those integrating image data and sensor-derived information, for early detection and monitoring of fish health, thereby reducing economic losses and improving animal welfare in aquaculture systems.

Intelligent Diagnosis of Fish Diseases Using Images and Computer Vision:

Fish diseases arise from a combination of biological pathogens, including parasites, fungi, bacteria, and viruses (Noga, 2010). Along with infectious agents, adverse physical and chemical conditions in the aquatic environment also contribute significantly to the onset of fish diseases (FAO, 2020). Fluctuations in water quality parameters, such as temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH, and chemical contaminants, can induce physiological stress in fish, thereby increasing their susceptibility to various diseases (Boyd, 2015). These stressors and disease processes manifest as external, behavioural, and internal tissue alterations, which serve as observable indicators of compromised fish health (Noga, 2010).

Camera and image systems can continuously observe fish populations in aquaculture environments and provide non-invasive monitoring without disturbing the animals (Føre *et*

al., 2018). Unlike conventional traditional inspection, “manual inspection of fish health is time consuming, subjective and often limited in frequency, whereas automated vision-based systems allow continuous and objective monitoring (Martins *et al.*, 2012). Vision-based monitoring enables *in situ* observation of fish and avoids the need for physical handling, which is known to induce stress and injury (Li *et al.*, 2024b), thereby reducing handling stress and injury to fish (Costa *et al.*, 2009). Fish disease diagnosis requires examination of multiple anatomical regions, including the skin, fins, gills, musculature, and internal organs (Noga, 2010). Alongside optical imaging, ultrasonic and imaging-assisted approaches have been investigated for detecting internal abnormalities in live fish under complex aquatic conditions (Bondad-Reantaso *et al.*, 2020). Diseased fish often exhibit visible surface abnormalities, including lesions, colour changes, and parasite attachment, which can be detected using image processing techniques.

Algorithms can detect red spots, open wounds, ulcers, and signs of haemorrhagic septicemia on the fish skin with high accuracy (Ahmed & Jeba, 2024). For example, underwater camera systems and a machine learning approach are being applied to count sea lice on salmon (Solvang and Hagemann 2018). Changes in colour, texture, and surface morphology are compared against healthy reference patterns, enabling automated differentiation between healthy and diseased fish (Li *et al.*, 2023a). Hu *et al.* designed a computer vision-based system for identifying infected fish and reported that “we used colour and texture features extracted from fish surface images to identify and classify diseases in Chinese carp” (Hu *et al.*, 2011). Digital image processing methods have also demonstrated the feasibility of detecting infected regions on the fish body surface and diagnosing fish diseases (Lyubchenko *et al.*, 2016). Fish length and body dimensions can be estimated automatically from images using computer vision techniques without removing the fish from the water (Costa *et al.*,

2009). Imaging approaches that measure fish length or body area from images and videos and relates these parameters to mass through statistical or model-based methods enable non-invasive size and mass estimation (Costa *et al.*, 2009). Such approaches reduce handling stress and allow frequent monitoring of growth performance in aquaculture systems (Martins *et al.*, 2012).

Recent studies have demonstrated that deep learning models, such as convolutional neural networks including ResNet50 and EfficientNet, can perform real-time fish disease detection by interpreting visual patterns in images, achieving higher accuracy than classical image processing methods (Mamun *et al.*, 2023; Rather *et al.*, 2024). Recent AI-driven automated systems further integrate real-time camera and sensor data to assess fish health, using machine learning techniques to enhance the precision and speed of disease identification (Zhang *et al.*, 2024a).

Reviews of AI applications in aquaculture confirm that artificial intelligence and machine learning are increasingly employed to analyze fish images for disease indicators and to improve automated health monitoring systems (Rather *et al.*, 2024; Zhang *et al.*, 2024b). This approach can help farmers detect and treat disease early, limiting the need for antibiotics and the risk of outbreaks. This method can assist Aquaculturists in identifying fish infections sooner, thereby enhancing treatment outcomes and reducing the risk of disease outbreaks in other fish populations.

Analyzing Swimming Behaviour:

Swimming behaviour is a sensitive indicator of fish health, as diseased or stressed fish often display abnormal movement patterns before clear external clinical signs appear (Martins *et al.*, 2012). Abnormal behaviours of fish under harsh conditions include irregular movement, reduced food intake, sluggish swimming, delayed response, loss of vertical equilibrium, departure from crowds, and tank floor scrubbing, which are standard indicators of physiological stress and disease (Jang

et al., 2022). Such behavioural deviations, including lethargy, erratic or circular swimming, spinning, and rubbing against nets or tank surfaces, are challenging to detect consistently through manual observation, particularly in high-density aquaculture systems. Lethargy is commonly observed in diseased or stressed fish and is characterized by reduced swimming speed, prolonged resting at the bottom of the tank, and isolation from the school (Liu *et al.*, 2024). Infected fish often exhibit lethargy, loss of appetite, and erratic swimming behaviour (Yue and Guo, 2025). Recent advances in artificial intelligence have enabled automated interpretation of these behavioural changes using computer vision and deep learning. Empirical results show that the DDEYOLOv9 algorithm can precisely identify and quantify abnormal fish behaviours in complex environments, indicating the capability of AI-based systems to detect variations in swimming patterns in real time (Li *et al.*, 2024). Besides, reviews of AI applications in aquaculture confirm that fish behaviour classification tracks and analyzes movement and extracts behavioural patterns, highlighting behavioural monitoring as a key component of intelligent health assessment systems (Al-Abri *et al.*, 2025). By continuously analyzing swimming trajectories, speed, and group dynamics using a camera, the fish are never touched, ensuring their welfare is maintained while data are collected (Yang *et al.*, 2020). AI systems can recognize abnormal movements faster and more objectively than humans, supporting early disease detection and improved health management in aquaculture.

Use of AI in Monitoring Water Quality:

Effective water quality monitoring is essential for the success and sustainability of aquaculture operations. As noted, effective water quality monitoring is paramount for the success of aquaculture operations (Lindholm-Lehto, 2023).

Real-Time Monitoring:

Temperature, colour, turbidity, and odour are the most basic physical parameters. Chemicals are key factors affecting water quality; hence, pH, dissolved oxygen (DO), organic carbon, suspended solids and total solids should be continuously monitored in real time. Physical, biological, and chemical parameters also interact with one another. For example, suspended solids can affect water turbidity, while temperature and chlorophyll can affect the amount of flora (Mohseni *et al.*, 2022). Real-time monitoring of water quality in oceans, surface waters, and accidental wastewater is possible due to the platform's agility, which enables high-accuracy data acquisition (Liu *et al.*, 2025). Recent studies indicate that AI algorithms can detect abnormal water-quality trends that may precede adverse health outcomes in cultured fish (Khurshid *et al.*, 2022). AI systems can anticipate future changes and provide early warnings to farmers (Rather *et al.*, 2024). For example, AI-based platforms have been developed to monitor microbial and bacterial contamination in water using automated data analysis (Gunda *et al.*, 2019). Temperature represents one of the most critical environmental factors in aquaculture, as it directly affects fish metabolism, growth, and immune function (Mugwanya *et al.*, 2022). AI algorithms integrated with temperature sensors enable continuous monitoring and anomaly detection. It has been shown that intelligent monitoring systems can issue real-time alerts when water temperature

deviates from species-specific optimal ranges, allowing farmers to take corrective actions promptly (Yang *et al.*, 2020).

Benefits for Fish Farmers:

AI-driven systems are capable of analyzing comprehensive datasets consisting of visual, environmental, and physiological data, enabling the identification of early disease symptoms, the prediction of potential health risks, and the guidance of timely interventions (Aung *et al.*, 2024). AI systems analyze information such as fish behaviour, water quality parameters, and environmental conditions to deliver precise feeding suggestions. This ensures feed is dispensed at optimal intervals and, thereby reducing feed wastage, improving feed conversion ratios, and promoting production efficiency (Atoum *et al.*, 2015; Zhang *et al.*, 2024). The usage of edge computing and advanced data analytics has enhanced the adaptability and efficiency of aquaculture operations (Cheng *et al.*, 2024). AI technologies facilitate various stages of processing, from quality assessment to packaging, reducing labour requirements and minimizing post-harvest losses while maintaining high product quality (Zhang *et al.*, 2023).

Figure 1. AI-based non-invasive system for fish health monitoring

Challenges:

High turbidity in aquaculture ponds significantly limits the performance of optical machine vision systems (Saberioon et al., 2017). Biofouling of sensors and cameras remains a major challenge in the persistent deployment of monitoring systems (Føre et al., 2018). One of the challenges is the high preliminary capital investment required to deploy infrastructures, including sensor networks, data transmission systems, and computational resources. Small- and medium-scale aquaculture operations often incur these upfront costs. Along with installation charges, ongoing costs of sensor maintenance, software

upgrades, data storage, and system calibration further intensify the financial burden and require specialized technical expertise (Kumaar et al., 2024). Developing AI algorithms and models that can efficiently capture and analyse these complex interactions is one of the significant challenges that will require continued research and development. Since AI systems depend on large amounts of sensitive data, there is a necessity to ensure that data is securely stored and transmitted, and that data privacy is maintained.

Conclusion:

Traditional methods of monitoring fish health are slow and stressful for fish, often detecting problems too late. Artificial Intelligence (AI) helps solve these issues by continuously monitoring fish health, swimming behaviour, and water quality without handling the fish.

Artificial Intelligence is not meant to replace the experience of fish farmers, but to support them as a smart assistant. Computer vision works as “smart eyes” underwater, while AI sensors help keep the water environment safe. Early detection of diseases allows farmers to take timely action, reducing fish deaths, economic losses, and unnecessary use of medicines.

Although challenges such as high costs and muddy water remain, affordable, effective AI technologies are likely to become common in aquaculture. Broadly, AI can lead to healthier fish, better farming practices, and more sustainable aquaculture in the future, with human expertise.

Recommendation:

To improve the use of Artificial Intelligence in aquaculture, simple, low-cost AI tools should be developed so that even small-scale fish farmers can use them easily. These tools should work well in muddy and unclear water, which is common in fish ponds. Government support, such as training programs and financial assistance, can encourage farmers to adopt these technologies. Clear rules and simple instructions should also be provided so farmers can use AI systems correctly.

Fish farmers should be trained to understand and use AI systems in their daily work. Learning how to read information from cameras and water sensors will help them take quick action to keep fish healthy. Good internet, safe data storage, and energy-saving devices will also help make AI use smoother. With proper training and support, AI can help farmers grow healthier fish and protect the environment.

References:

1. Ahmed, M. S., & Jeba, S. M. (2024). SalmonScan: A novel image dataset for machine learning and deep learning analysis in fish disease detection in aquaculture. *Data in Brief*, 54, 110388. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2024.110388>
2. Al-Abri, S., Keshvari, S., Al-Rashdi, K., Al-Hmouz, R., & Bourdoucen, H. (2025). Computer vision-based approaches for fish monitoring systems: A comprehensive study. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 58, Article 185. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-025-11180-3>
3. Atoum, Y., Srivastava, S., & Liu, X. (2015). Automatic feeding control for dense aquaculture fish tanks. *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, 22(8), 1089–1093. <https://doi.org/10.1109/LSP.2014.2385794>
4. Aung, T., Abdul Razak, R., & Rahiman Bin Md Nor, A. (2025). Artificial intelligence methods used in various aquaculture applications: A systematic literature review. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society*, 56(1), e13107. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jwas.13107>
5. Badiola, M., Mendiola, D., & Bostock, J. (2012). Recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) analysis: Main issues on management and future challenges. *Aquacultural Engineering*, 51, 26–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaeng.2012.07.004>
6. Barton, B. A. (2002). Stress in fishes: A diversity of responses with particular reference to changes in circulating corticosteroids. *Integrative and Comparative Biology*, 42(3), 517–525. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icb/42.3.517>
7. Béné, C., Barange, M., Subasinghe, R., Pinstrup-Andersen, P., Hemre, G.-I., & Williams, M. (2015). Feeding 9 billion by 2050 – Putting fish back on the menu. *Food*

- Security, 7, 261–274.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12571-015-0427-z>
8. Bohara, D. K., & Rana, K. (2024). Unmasking teachers' proficiency in harnessing artificial intelligence for transformative education. *SN Social Sciences*, 4, 203.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s43545-024-01003-7>
 9. Bondad-Reantaso, M. G., Lavilla-Pitogo, C. R., Karunasagar, I., Arthur, J. R., Hao, B., Irde, E., Garrido-Gamarro, E., & Peñarubia, O. R. (2020). Outputs and activities of FAO project on antimicrobial resistance in aquaculture (FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Circular No. 1215). FAO.
<https://doi.org/10.4060/cb1209en>
 10. Boyd, C. E. (2015). *Water quality: An introduction*. Springer.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-17446-4>
 11. Cheng, W. K., Khor, J. C., Liew, W. Z., Bea, K. T., & Chen, Y. L. (2024). Integration of federated learning and edge-cloud platform for precision aquaculture. *IEEE Access*, 12, 124974–124989.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3454057>
 12. Costa, C., Scardi, M., Vitalini, V., & Cataudella, S. (2009). A dual camera system for counting and sizing northern bluefin tuna during transfer to aquaculture cages. *Aquaculture*, 291(3–4), 161–167.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2009.02.013>
 13. Damodar, T., Singh, B., Prabhu, N., Marate, S., Gowda, V. K., Lalitha, A. V., D'Souza, F. S., Sajjan, S. V., Kariyappa, M., Kinhal, U. V., Prathyusha, P. V., Desai, A., Thennarasu, K., Solomon, T., Ravi, V., & Yadav, R. (2023). Association of scrub typhus in children with acute encephalitis syndrome. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, 29(4), 711–722. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2904.221157>
 14. FAO. (2020). *The state of world fisheries and aquaculture 2020: Sustainability in action*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
 15. FAO. (2022). *The state of world fisheries and aquaculture 2022*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
 16. Føre, M., Frank, K., Norton, T., Svendsen, E., Alfredsen, J. A., Dempster, T., & Berckmans, D. (2018). Precision fish farming: A new framework to improve production in aquaculture. *Biosystems Engineering*, 173, 176–193.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2017.10.014>
 17. Gunda, K. S., Gautam, S. H., & Mitra, S. K. (2019). Artificial intelligence-based mobile application for water quality monitoring. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*, 166, B3031. <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0081909jes>
 18. HLPE. (2014). *Sustainable fisheries and aquaculture for food security and nutrition*. High Level Panel of Experts.
 19. Hu, J., Li, D., Duan, Q., Chen, G., & Si, X. (2011). Preliminary design of a recognition system for infected fish species using computer vision. In *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Computer and Computing Technologies in Agriculture* (pp. 530–534).
 20. Jang, J. C., Kim, Y. R., Bak, S., Jang, S. W., & Kim, J. M. (2022). Abnormal behaviour in rock bream detected using deep learning-based image analysis. *Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 25(3), 151–157.
<https://doi.org/10.47853/FAS.2022.e13>
 21. Khurshid, H., Mumtaz, R., Alvi, N., Haque, A., Mumtaz, S., Shafait, F., Ahmed, S., Malik, M. I., & Dengel, A. (2022). Bacterial prediction using IoT and machine learning. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 194, 133. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-021-09698-4>
 22. Kumar, A. S., Vignesh, A. V., & Deepak, K. (2024). FishNet freshwater fish disease detection using deep learning techniques. In

- Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Advancement in Computation & Computer Technologies (pp. 368–373).
23. Li, W., Liu, Y., Wang, W., Li, Z., & Yue, J. (2024a) TFMFT: Transformer-based multiple fish tracking. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 217, 108600. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2023.108600>
24. Li, Y., Hu, Z., Zhang, Y., Liu, J., Tu, W., & Yu, H. (2024b). DDEYOLOv9: Detecting and counting abnormal fish behaviors. *Fishes*, 9(6), 242. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fishes9060242>
25. Lindholm-Lehto, P. (2023). Water quality monitoring in recirculating aquaculture systems. *Aquaculture, Fish and Fisheries*, 3, 113–131. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aff2.10>
26. Lyubchenko, V., Matarneh, R., Kobylin, O., & Lyashenko, V. (2016). Digital image processing techniques for detection and diagnosis of fish diseases. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering*, 6(4), 79–83.
27. Maluazi, Nur & Zulkifley, Mohd Asyraf & Kadim, Zulaikha. (2024). A Concise Review on Deep Learning Methods in Agricultural Applications. 507-511. 10.1109/IMSA61967.2024.10652847.
28. Mamun, M. R. I., Rahman, U. S., Akter, T., & Azim, M. (2023). Fish disease detection using deep learning and machine learning. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 185(21). <https://doi.org/10.5120/ijca2023923079>
29. Martins, C. I. M., Galhardo, L., Noble, C., Damsgård, B., Spedicato, M. T., Zupa, W., & Kristiansen, T. (2012). Behavioural indicators of welfare in farmed fish. *Fish Physiology and Biochemistry*, 38, 17–41. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10695-011-9518-8>
30. Mohseni, F., Saba, F., Mirmazloumi, S. M., Amani, M., Mokhtarzade, M., Jamali, S., & Mahdavi, S. (2022). Ocean water quality monitoring using remote sensing techniques: A review. *Marine Environmental Research*, 180, 105701.
31. Mugwanya, M., Dawood, M., Kimera, F., & Sewilam, H. (2022). Influence of stocking density on fish behavior and immunity in RAS. *Annals of Animal Science*, 22. <https://doi.org/10.2478/aoas-2022-0014>
32. Naylor, R. L., Hardy, R. W., Buschmann, A. H., et al. (2021). A 20-year retrospective review of global aquaculture. *Nature*, 591, 551–563. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03308-6>
33. Noga, E. J. (2010). *Fish disease: Diagnosis and treatment* (2nd ed.). Wiley-Blackwell.
34. Rather, M., Ahmad, I., Shah, A., Hajam, Y. A., Amin, A., Khursheed, S., & Rasool, S. (2024). Exploring opportunities of artificial intelligence in aquaculture to meet increasing food demand. *Food Chemistry X*, 22, 101309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fochx.2024.101309>
35. Ringø, E., Van Doan, H., Lee, S. H., Soltani, M., Hoseinifar, S. H., Harikrishnan, R., & Song, S. K. (2020). Probiotics and bacilli in aquaculture. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 129(1), 116–136. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.14628>
36. Saberioon, M. M., & Cisar, P. (2016). Automated multiple fish tracking in three dimensions. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 121, 215–221.
37. Shinn AP, Pratoomyot J, Bron JE, Paladini G, Brooker EE, Brooker AJ. Economic costs of protistan and metazoan parasites to global mariculture. *Parasitology*. 2015 Jan;142(1):196-270. doi: 10.1017/S0031182014001437. Epub 2014 Dec 2. PMID: 25438750.
38. Solvang, T., & Hagemann, A. (2018). Machine vision system for sea lice behaviour. *Journal of Experimental Biology*, 221, jeb183277.

39. Stofa, M., Azizan, F. A. Z., & Zulkifley, M. A. (2025). A review of deep learning methods in aquatic animal husbandry. *PeerJ Computer Science*, 11, e3105. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.3105>
40. Tacon, Albert & Metian, Marc. (2015). Feed Matters: Satisfying the Feed Demand of Aquaculture. *Reviews in Fisheries Science & Aquaculture*. 23. 1-10. [10.1080/23308249.2014.987209](https://doi.org/10.1080/23308249.2014.987209).
41. Yang, L., Liu, Y., Yu, H., Fang, X., Song, L., Li, D., & Chen, Y. (2020). Computer vision models in intelligent aquaculture. *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering*, 28, 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11831-020-09486-2>
42. Yue, G., & Guo, C. (2025). Strategies for managing major diseases in Asian seabass aquaculture. *Animal Diseases*, 5, 6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s44149-025-00159-w>
43. Zhang, L., Li, Y., Gu, Y., Fu, Y., Zhang, X., & Hu, J. (2024b). Atlantic salmon adulteration authentication using machine learning. *Microchemical Journal*, 196, 109638. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2023.109638>
44. Zhang, R., Chen, X., Wan, Z., Wang, M., & Xiao, X. (2023). Deep learning-based oyster packaging system. *Applied Sciences*, 13(24), 13105. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app132413105>
45. Zhang, T., Yang, Y., Liu, Y., Liu, C., Zhao, R., Li, D., & Shi, C. (2024a). Fully automatic system